

ANALYSIS OF ROAD TRANSPORT INCIDENTS AND THE FACTORS CAUSING THEM

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, large-scale organizational and practical work has been carried out in our country to improve the road safety system. Define the following as urgent directions for ensuring road safety in the country. Improving road infrastructure and improving its quality, creating reliable conditions for the safe movement of road users based on the priority of pedestrian-public transport and cycling; bringing the educational process to a qualitatively new level by introducing innovative pedagogical technologies into the system of training, retraining, and advanced training of drivers; and increasing the culture of compliance with traffic rules among drivers and pedestrians.

Analysis and results; Methodology for investigating a vehicle collision with a pedestrian. Road traffic accidents involving pedestrian collisions, despite their extreme diversity, possess common patterns that allow for the use of a unified research methodology based largely on the synchrony and interconnection of pedestrian and driver actions and the calculation of the situation's development on a single time scale. Experts and specialists may be asked the following questions:

Figure 1. The state of a pedestrian before being struck by a car.

The study should begin with the analysis of the diagram taken from the scene of the traffic accident and the construction of a scale diagram. The most critical task is to determine the positions of the pedestrian and the vehicle at the moment of impact (first contact). If traces of tire slippage are present and recorded at the scene of the traffic accident, it will be possible to determine the sp-transverse coordinate of the collision site with sufficient accuracy based on vehicle bruises and pedestrian injuries.

Fig. 2. The state of the vehicle when it hits a pedestrian.

The speed of the vehicle at the start of initial and intensive braking, and at the moment of impact, respectively; s_u is the distance of the vehicle from the pedestrian's line; s_{yu} is the length of the vehicle's braking tracks (slip tracks) at the scene; s_n is the distance traveled by the vehicle in the braking position after impact; s_p is the distance traveled by the pedestrian from the moment the danger arose until impact; and s_{pn} is the distance traveled by the vehicle in the braking position with constant deceleration. The longitudinal coordinate of the collision site can be determined based on the trajectory of the vehicle's movement relative to any visible points on the edge of the carriageway (post, road sign, well, pavilion, tree, etc.), as well as the indications of the injured pedestrian, as well as the presence of debris streams from under the front fenders, eyewitnesses to the traffic accident, passengers in the vehicle, and the driver. In this case, if the pedestrian moved not in a transverse direction relative to the road, but at some acute angle relative to the road line, it is necessary to coordinate the longitudinal coordinate with the transverse coordinate and the pedestrian's injuries.

Conclusions and suggestions; The quality of traffic flow is characterized by the level of comfort, level of service, smooth movement, ease of driving, etc. The level of service is characterized by the following factors: speed and time spent on the trip, break in movement, freedom of maneuver, safety, ease of driving, operating costs. All these indicators are interconnected: for example, when the intensity of movement changes, speed, safety and ease of movement, freedom of maneuver, and others change.

The intensity and speed of movement have a significant impact on operational costs, mobility comfort, traffic safety, and travel time. Pedestrians cross the road on average two to three times during their movement, and may also have to cross railways, waterways, or other natural objects. One of our main tasks is to ensure the convenience and safety of their movement when crossing roads. Therefore, the proper design, construction, and

reconstruction of relevant crossings should be the primary consideration when developing pedestrian routes.

The main causes of pedestrian collisions are the unsatisfactory condition of the pedestrian crossing and its equipment, which is often caused by drivers' failure to comply with traffic rules. It has been proven that every sixth traffic accident involving a pedestrian at a pedestrian crossing occurs precisely for this reason due to psychophysiological factors of the pedestrian, such as the natural desire to save time by choosing the shortest route, thereby violating traffic rules, the physiological characteristics of pedestrians, and therefore the placement of technical means for organizing pedestrian traffic, all structures developed taking into account their rapid and accurate perception of weather conditions: rain, mud, fog, etc. large vehicles blocking the pedestrian crossing sign unsatisfactory condition of vehicles, especially during the spring-autumn thaw period..

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